

IMMUNE ADAPTATION PROCESS AND RISK OF EARLY NEONATAL COMPLICATIONS IN INFANTS BORN OF MOTHERS WITH AUTOIMMUNE DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the incidence of autoimmune diseases, in particular, Systemic lupus erythematosus, Rheumatoid arthritis and Autoimmune thyroiditis, has been increasing among women of reproductive age. Transplacental transfer of maternal autoantibodies and chronic inflammatory processes can affect the formation of the fetal immune system. This increases the risk of immune adaptation disorders and early complications in the neonatal period.

Relevance. In recent years, the incidence of autoimmune diseases, in particular, Systemic lupus erythematosus, Rheumatoid arthritis and Autoimmune thyroiditis, has been increasing among women of reproductive age. Transplacental transfer of maternal autoantibodies and chronic inflammatory processes can affect the formation of the fetal immune system. This increases the risk of immune adaptation disorders and early complications in the neonatal period.

Objective. To assess the characteristics of the immune adaptation process and the risk of early neonatal complications in newborns born to mothers with autoimmune diseases.

Materials and methods. The study included 2 groups: the main group - 45 infants born to mothers with autoimmune diseases; the control group - 45 infants born to healthy mothers. Peripheral blood immune indices (IgG, IgM, lymphocyte subpopulations), inflammatory markers and clinical status in the early neonatal period were analyzed in infants.

Results. According to the results of the study, significant differences were found in the immune system indicators in infants born to mothers with autoimmune diseases. In the main group, the level of IgG was on average 18–22% higher than in the control group ($p < 0.05$), which was explained by autoantibodies transferred transplacentally from the mother. There was no significant difference in the level of IgM ($p > 0.05$), which indicates that endogenous synthesis is not yet sufficiently formed in the neonatal period. In the analysis of lymphocyte subpopulations, the proportion of CD4⁺ T-lymphocytes decreased (by an average of 12%),

and the proportion of CD8+ cells increased relatively, as a result of which a decrease in the immunoregulatory index was detected ($p < 0.05$). Also, the levels of C-reactive protein and proinflammatory cytokines (IL-6) were higher in the main group. Clinically, in the main group of infants, respiratory disorders in the early neonatal period occurred in 26% of cases, hyperbilirubinemia in 34% of cases, and infectious complications in 22% of cases, which is a significantly higher rate than in the control group ($p < 0.05$). Premature birth and low body weight were also more often recorded in the main group. The results obtained confirm that the process of adaptation of the fetal immune system in an autoimmune background is complicated and the risk of early neonatal complications is increased.

Conclusion. The process of immune adaptation in infants born to mothers with autoimmune diseases is peculiar and the risk of early neonatal complications is high. Early immune monitoring and an individual preventive approach are important in this group of infants.

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